

Kinetics and Mechanism of Nucleophilic Substitution in Tri-*p*-Iodo Benzyl Phosphate in Acidic Medium†

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Manuscript received 18 July 1975; revised 2 January 1976; accepted 3 March 1976.

The kinetic data in 50% aq dioxan at 80° in the region 0.5M to 4.5M hydrochloric acid shows that tri-*p*-iodo benzyl phosphate is reactive mainly via conjugate acid species. Unlike other triesters the hydrolysis of tri-*p*-iodo benzyl phosphate has been found to be accompanied by concomitant nucleophilic substitution by chloride ion. Ionic strength data shows positive salt effect. Rate coefficients estimated for acid catalysed hydrolysis together with those computed by the presumption of chloride ion substitution reaction, are in close agreement with the experimentally observed rates. Temperature, solvent, solvent-isotope, substrate concentration effects, etc. have been studied.

THE determination of mechanism of hydrolysis of organic phosphates is expected to reveal the possible correlation between the reaction paths of chemical and enzymic hydrolysis of biologically important phosphate esters¹. Kinetics of hydrolysis of triesters derived from orthophosphoric acid have not been studied much². Hydrolysis of trimethyl³ and triphenyl³ phosphates have been studied but mechanisms have not been suggested. Tri (2, 3-dimethoxyphenyl) phosphate is hydrolysed into inorganic phosphate by the mechanism which does not include the diester as an intermediate⁴. Nucleophilic substitution of tri-*p*-iodo benzyl phosphate has now been investigated. Due to structural differences, tri-*p*-iodo benzyl phosphate may not only exhibit changes in reaction rates, but new reaction paths may also be involved.

Materials and methods

p-Toluidine was converted into *p*-iodo toluene⁵. The latter on bromination⁵ changed into *p*-iodo benzyl bromide (m. p. 78.75°). Tri-*p*-iodo benzyl phosphate was prepared using *p*-iodo benzyl bromide and silver phosphate⁶. The crude product so obtained was finally recrystallised (m. p. 164°) from ethanol (Found: C, 33.94; H, 2.45; P, 4.43 percent. Calc. for C₂₁H₁₈PO₄I₃: C, 33.80; H, 2.43; P, 4.15 percent). Deuterium oxide (>99.4%) was procured from B.A.R.C. Bombay. Dioxan was purified⁷ before use. Constant ionic strengths were maintained using mixtures of HCl and NaCl. All the chemicals used belonged to BDH (A.R.) and Riedel qualities. Colorimetric method⁸ was used for the estimation of inorganic phosphate. The kinetic runs were carried out at 80° ± 0.° employing 5 × 10⁻⁴ M solutions of the ester in dioxan-water (50 : 50 v/v) unless otherwise specified. First order rates of the hydrolysis of triester were corrected by graphical or mirror method⁹ taking into account the rates of hydrolysis of diester studied under similar experimental conditions¹⁰.

Results and Discussion

The kinetic data of the hydrolysis of tri-*p*-iodo benzyl phosphate in the region 0.5 to 4.5 M hydrochloric acid show that the rate of reaction increases much rapidly with the rise in acidity (Fig. 1). Unusual rise in rate may happen due to a strong positive effect of the ionic strength. Since the rate is measured by estimating inorganic phosphate as a final product, the rate of reaction of the triester has been evaluated by the mirror method⁹ (Fig. 1). The rate coefficients are uniformly higher in the region studied. Similar results were also obtained for the hydrolysis of other phosphate esters¹¹.

Fig. 1. Hydrolysis of Tri-*p*-iodo benzyl phosphate in HCl acid and 50% aqueous Dioxan (v/v) at 80°C.

[—○— Curve for experimental rates; (---) theoretical rates;

—△— Mirror method rates.]

† Taken from the Ph.D. Thesis of Shri Anil V. Killedar, Jiwaji University, 1972.

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Fig. 2. Hydrolysis of tri-*p*-Iodo benzyl phosphate at constant ionic strength in 50% Aqueous Dioxan (v/v) at 80°.

Kinetic data at constant ionic strength indicate acid catalysis. Plot between rate constants and acid molarities show that three linear curves with positive slope meet at origin (Fig.). This suggests negligible contribution from hydrolysis via neutral species to the acid catalysed reaction. The latter is subject to a positive effect of the ionic strength as the slopes (specific acid catalysed rates k_H^+) increase with the increase in ionic strength.

$$k_H^+ = k_{H_0}^+ \cdot \exp. b_H^+ \cdot \mu \quad (1)$$

Debye-Hückel relation (1) between rate and ionic strength inevitably holds as evidenced by a linear curve (not given) between ionic strength versus log specific acid catalysed rate from which $k_{H_0}^+$ (the specific acid catalysed rate at zero ionic strength) and $b_H^+ = b'_H + / 2.303$ (a constant) can be determined. The acid catalysed rates (Table 1) have been calculated by the equation :

$$\log k_H^+ \cdot C_H^+ = \log k_{H_0}^+ + b'_H \cdot \mu + \log C_H^+ \quad (2)$$

Results show that the estimated rates do not agree with the observed rates, the deviation between these increases

TABLE 1—OBSERVED AND ACID CATALYSED RATES FOR THE HYDROLYSIS OF TRI-*p*-IODO BENZYL PHOSPHATE IN 50% AQUEOUS DIOXAN AT 80°

Acid (M)	$10^8 k_H^+ \cdot C_H^+$ (min. ⁻¹) (calcd)	$10^8 k_d$ (min. ⁻¹) (obsd.)
0.5	1.16	1.01
1.0	2.95	3.16
1.5	5.64	6.65
2.0	9.57	11.08
2.5	15.24	23.70
3.0	23.29	41.07
3.5	34.60	73.36
4.0	51.36	120.00
4.5	72.14	155.80

with the increase in acidity. This may be attributed to a side reaction of chloride ions with the conjugate acid species. Trimethyl phosphate has been found to be susceptible to the attack of halide ions¹². Presuming the overall rate of the reaction to be governed by both hydrolysis and bimolecular nucleophilic substitution by the chloride ion, the specific rate of the reaction between the chloride ion and conjugate acid species have been determined by the equation :

$$k_e (\text{obsd.}) = k_H^+ \cdot C_H^+ + k_{Cl^-} \cdot C_{Cl^-} \quad (3)$$

Since the concentrations of the halide ion is the same as those of hydrogen ion :

$$k_e (\text{obsd.}) = k_H^+ \cdot C_H^+ + k_{Cl^-} \cdot C_H^+ \quad (4)$$

and therefore,

$$k_{Cl^-} = \frac{k_e (\text{obsd.}) - k_H^+ \cdot C_H^+}{(C_H^+)} \quad (5)$$

TABLE 2—NUCLEOPHILIC SUBSTITUTION OF TRI-*p*-IODO BENZYL PHOSPHATE BY CHLORIDE ION IN 50% AQ. DIOXAN AT 80°.

HCl (M)	$10^8 k_{Cl^-}$ (min. ⁻¹) (calcd.)	$4 + \log k_{Cl^-}$ (calcd.)
1.0	0.21	0.32
1.5	0.67	0.83
2.0	0.75	0.88
2.5	3.38	1.53
3.0	5.97	1.78
3.5	11.07	2.04
4.0	17.16	2.23
4.5	18.59	2.27

The specific rate constants for the halide reaction (k_{Cl^-}) so estimated have been summarised in Table 2. Just as k_H^+ is related to ionic strength exponentially, similar relation for k_{Cl^-} may be written as :

$$k_{Cl^-} = k_{Cl_0^-} \cdot \exp. b_{Cl^-} \cdot (\mu) \quad (6)$$

where k_{Cl^-} , $k_{Cl_0^-}$, b_{Cl^-} and μ for halide ion reactions are the specific rate constants at that ionic strength, the specific rate constant at zero ionic strength, a constant and ionic strength respectively.

The above presumption that the overall rate of reaction of the triester in acid medium is made up of two concomitant reactions is proved by a linear curve (Fig. 3) between ionic strength and $\log k_{Cl^-}$ (specific rate constant for the halide ion reaction). Intercept on the log rate axis gives $k_{Cl_0^-} = 13.34 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ min.}^{-1}$ and the slope is $b'_{Cl^-} = 0.536$. The rate constants for halide ion reaction calculated by the above equation together with the calculated acid catalysed rates are in close

Fig. 3. Nucleophilic Substitution of Tri-*p*-Iodobenzyl Phosphate by chloride ion at 80° [Solvent 50% Aqueous Dioxan v/v]

agreement with the observed rates (Table 3). In 4.5 M acid solution the reaction is represented by

$$k_e (\text{calcd.}) = k_{H^+} \cdot C_{H^+} \cdot \exp. b_{H^+} \cdot \mu (a_{H_2O})^n + k_{Cl^-} \cdot C_{Cl^-} \cdot \exp. b_{Cl^-} \cdot \mu (a_{H_2O})^n \quad (7)$$

The participation of the side reaction is supported by this agreement and also by the failure of the mirror method, which does not bring about such an agreement. It has been also shown that iodide ions convert triesters into diesters⁶.

TABLE 3—OBSERVED AND CALCULATED RATES FOR THE REACTIONS OF TRI-*p*-IODO BENZYL PHOSPHATE IN ACID MEDIUM AT 80°. [Solvent 50% aqueous dioxan (v/v)]

HCl (M)	10 ⁵ k _{H⁺} · C _{H⁺} (min. ⁻¹)	10 ⁵ k _{Cl⁻} · C _{Cl⁻} (min. ⁻¹)	10 ⁵ k _e (calcd.) (min. ⁻¹)	10 ⁵ k _e (obsd.) (min. ⁻¹)
1.0	2.95	0.46	3.41	3.16
1.5	5.64	1.27	6.91	6.65
2.0	9.57	3.15	12.72	11.08
2.5	15.24	7.29	22.53	23.70
3.0	23.29	16.22	39.51	41.07
3.5	34.60	35.07	69.67	73.36
4.0	51.36	74.32	125.68	120.00
4.5	39.64 ^b	117.20 ^a	156.84	155.80

a,b—The value of n in (a_{H₂O}) in equation 7 varies as 1 and 2 respectively.

Solvent-isotope effect in 1 M hydrochloric acid replacing H₂O by D₂O (k_{D₂O}/k_{medium} = 1.38) indicates the formation of conjugate acid species by fast pre-equilibrium proton transfer in specific acid catalysed reaction¹³. Arrhenius parameters at 70°, 80° and 90° in 2.0 M HCl (where contribution by the acid catalysed rate is much more than the chloride ion reaction) have been found to be E = 27.01 k. cal./mole, ΔS[‡] = -1.58 e. u. and frequency factor = 8.75 × 10¹² sec.⁻¹. These results are consistent with the unimolecular nature of acid catalysed hydrolysis¹⁴. A plot of log acid catalysed rates versus -H₀ (slope 1.05), shows specific acid catalysed unimolecular hydrolysis of tri-*p*-iodo benzyl phosphate¹⁵. Similar findings were also noted for the hydrolysis of β-propiolactone¹⁶ and allyl phosphate¹⁷.

TABLE 4—INFLUENCE OF SOLVENT ON THE ACID HYDROLYSIS OF TRI-*p*-IODO BENZYL PHOSPHATE AT 80°

HCl (M)	Dioxane (% v/v)	10 ⁵ k _e (min. ⁻¹) (obsd.)
2.0	50	11.08
2.0	60	12.84
2.0	70	14.26

Kinetic data in a series of aqueous dioxan mixture in 2.0 M HCl at 80° show that the rate increases with the increase in dioxan content (Table 4). The significant elevation in the reaction rate may be assigned to the intrinsically high proton donating ability of dioxan-water solution in acid medium¹⁸. Pseudo-first order rate constants observed at 2.0 M HCl are independent of substrate (Table 5), indicating kinetic first order with respect to ester. Bunnett parameters (not given) w and w* are the slopes of plots between log k + H₀ and log k - log CH+ and log a_{H₂O} respectively. When the value of w¹s - 2.5 to 0 the reaction is taken to be unimolecular¹⁹, w for the acid catalysed hydrolysis of Tri-*p*-iodo benzyl phosphate is -0.83 indicating the reaction to be unimolecular. The other parameter w*, as expected has small curvature.

TABLE 5—INFLUENCE OF [SUBSTRATE] ON THE RATE CONSTANTS OF HYDROLYSIS OF TRI-*p*-IODO BENZYL PHOSPHATE AT 80°. [Solvent : 50% Aq. Dioxan (v/v)]

HCl (M)	Substrate (M)	10 ⁵ k _e (min. ⁻¹) (obsd.)
2.0	0.0003	11.08
2.0	0.0004	11.23
2.0	0.0005	11.08
2.0	0.0006	10.98

The conjugate acid species of the ester is more likely to be cleaved at C - O linkage rather than P - O bond, as the *p*-iodo benzyl cation formed subsequently as reaction intermediate would be greatly stabilised by the +M (electron releasing) mesomeric effect of the iodo-substituent.

Fig. 4. Isokinetic relationship for the hydrolysis of Phosphate Triesters via conjugate acid species.

The probability of C-O fission is also supported by the linear plot of isokinetic relationship (Fig. 4) with other related triesters which involve C-O fission. Based on the results gathered, the overall mechanism of the reactions of tri-*p*-iodo benzyl phosphate in acid medium may be represented as shown in Chart 1 and Chart 2. This is followed by the hydrolysis of diester into monoester and then finally into inorganic phosphate¹⁰.

Acknowledgement

The author (A. V. K.) is thankful to the C. S. I. R., New Delhi for financial help by providing research fellowship.

Chart 1. Probable reaction path for the acid hydrolysis of Tri-*p*-iodo benzyl phosphate involving formation of conjugate acid species and unimolecular heterolysis of C-O linkage.

Chart 2. Mechanism of Nucleophilic bimolecular substitution reaction of Tri-*p*-iodobenzylphosphate by chloride ion.

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